

CHARACTERIZATION AND GENERATION OF MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTES IN NORTH EASTERN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study focused on the characterization and generation of municipal solid waste in the north eastern part of Nigeria. Daily samples were collected and interpreted using Microsoft Excel for quantification purposes while the characterization samples were collected during the months of February, March and April and during the raining season in August. The refuse physical characteristics were then evaluated by sifting through the waste and separate it into its various physical major components. They were analyzed for proximate and ultimate composition using ASTM standards. Average moisture contents were found to vary from 21.917 to 24.326. Wood, paper, plastic and leaves were found in varying proportions and 1.2 kg was found to be the daily average generation of waste, per person. The lower calorific values (CV) of the refuse in the area of study were found to be low and could not sustain industrial incineration. To make up to the low CVs in the incineration process, a supplementary fuel; as sugar cane straw, weeds; was needed. The knowledge of the refuse CV alone is not enough to conclude whether the refuse will burn or not. Its moisture content is also an essential parameter.

KEYWORDS: municipal solid waste, generation, characterization, north eastern Nigeria, ultimate analysis, proximate analysis, calorific value.

INTRODUCTION

Majority of these items being used daily are thrown away rather disposed of. In developing countries where waste management systems are insufficient and inefficient, coupled with the expanding urban population (Daskalopoulos *et al.*, 1998; Ehrlich & Ehrlich, 1972), the problem is reaching proportions that are cause for major concern. A full understanding of refuse characteristics is crucial in the decision making stage when the “best option disposal” is to be made (Menard 2003, Diso *et al.* 1995). These wastes can immensely impact water quality and sanitation if left untreated (Oumarou *et al.*, 2011).

Developed countries are engaged in new technology for waste avoidance, recycling and reuse, while developing countries are still wrestling to decide on the best option to treat and dispose of waste (Mudzafar, 1996). Wastes produced in the municipality (i.e. industrial wastes, hospital wastes, municipal wastes, etc) influence water and sanitation by ways of runoffs and leachates into water ponds, streams and underground water ways.

Semi-arid regions of the world are defined as the transition zones between arid and sub humid belts and precipitation is less than potential evaporation, characterized by high temperatures (30°C- 45°C) in the hottest months (SFSA 2007). In Africa, these regions are mainly characterized by low annual rainfall and the whole area is mainly desertique. These represent about 35% of the lands in Nigeria and house more than 50 million people (National Bureau of Statistics, 2006). The National energy supplies are at present almost entirely dependent on fossil fuels and firewood which are depleting fast (Ikuponisi, 2006). Dauda and Osita (2003) determined the composition of solid wastes and their mode of disposal for north –eastern cities of Maiduguri, Damaturu and proposed their efficient solid waste management options through re-use. Coker *et al.* (2003), after emphasizing the effect of septic sludge apart from solid wastes and industrial hazardous wastes, highlighted the practices of the population in Ibadan, where people use septic sludge mixed with human faeces and urine for agriculture. They suggested land filling of the trench type which involves the excavation of deep trenches as an Appropriate Management Option (AMO). Mengiseny and Josia (2010) are of the opinion too that the main problem facing policy makers in the waste management sector is how to predict the amount of solid wastes generated in the near future in order to devise the appropriate treatment or disposal mechanism. Agunwamba *et al.* (1998) analyzed the waste in Onitsha (Nigeria). Also in the southern part of the country, Adeyemi *et al.* (2004) investigated the impact of waste scavenger in case study of Ilorin. Jekayinfa and Omisakin (2005)

considered ten agricultural wastes in Nigeria to determine their energy content using the method of Association of official Analytical Chemists. Results of their analysis showed that the mean higher heating values of the wastes samples were 16505kJ/kg, 19597kJ/kg, 20647kJ/kg, 15891kJ/kg, 17303kJ/kg, 19458kJ/kg, 28203kJ/kg, 19299kJ/kg, 21392kJ/kg and 21143kJ/kg for groundnut shell, yam peels, coconut shell, mango peels, palm oil mill effluent, corn cob, cherry, orange peels, melon shell and black walnut hull respectively. All the waste samples considered have heat values greater than some well-known biomass-fuels and fall within the limit for the production of steam in electricity generation.

Paolo (2010) investigated the effect of separate collection of municipal solid waste on the calorific value of the residual waste. He emphasised that separate collection plays an irreplaceable role in solid waste management and incineration. Considering the average Italian municipal solid waste composition, he proposed separate collection scenarios different from those tested; he proposed a regression model, calibrated it and tested it partially.

Ogaji *et al.* (2007) investigated the municipal solid waste (MSW) generated in Port Harcourt. They found it in large quantities, but some remains as litter in parts of the municipality. Refuse is mostly buried, but some reckless open-burning ensues, so posing environmental hazards. Waste collected from different receptacles and dumpsites in the city was subjected to analysis: on average, it consisted of 66.6% volatile solids, 13.5% fixed solids, 19.1% liquid and 0.8% other components. They also found an average biodegradability fraction is 0.807, with a carbon-to-nitrogen ratio of 27:1. The energy content of the refuse was 7.25 MJ/kg as collected. These results indicate that such refuse is amenable to several disposal options with less adverse impact on the environment.

This paper treats the generation and determination of wastes characteristics in the north eastern semiarid region of Nigeria; their primary sources, and their availability through collection, sampling, separation and laboratory analysis. Determination of the wastes combustion characteristics and evaluation of the amount of energy to be obtained from such wastes was also carried out.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data collection: Daily data on the waste load weights collected by the trucks of the municipalities were used. To this were added the door-to door and dump -to- dump data collected, because not all parts have access to collection by trucks. Other information was provided by the various States Environmental Protection agencies of the study area. The entire population of the study area selected cities was considered in order to obtain a per capita estimate, according to the National Bureau of Statistics data of 2006. Generation rates of MSW were obtained using Equation (1).

$$PCG = \left[\frac{\left(\frac{\text{Waste generated}}{\text{Weeks}} \right) \left(\frac{\text{Weeks}}{\text{Days}} \right)}{\text{Population}} \right] \text{ (kg/day. person)} \quad (1)$$

where PCG is the per capita waste generation

Laboratory analysis: Samples considered were collected during the months of February, March and April and during the raining season in the month of August. The refuse characteristics were then evaluated by sifting through the waste and separate it into its various physical major components. It should be noted that all samples taken at the various refuse dumping sites contain a large proportion of sand which had to be removed prior to any measurement. This is due to the fact that sand is an inert element in the combustion process. Furthermore, a fist sieving is carried out followed by hand picking, carried out to remove small stones which could not pass through the sieve.

The sample was then sieved again using a 2 mm mesh sieve, before being ground to powder form using a small porcelain mortar and pestle.

Equipment: A digital METTLER TOLEDO AB 54 weighting machine (limitations: 10 mg minimum and 51 grams maximum); a digital Spectrometer SPECTRUMLAB 22 PC as well as a Gerhardt - Kjeldatherm machine. Glass ware equipment includes 16 pieces of PYREX conical flasks, pipettes, burettes, beaker, volumetric flask, plastic bottles and filter papers.

The reagents are: Sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄), Orthophosphoric acid (H₃PO₄), Ferrous sulphate (FeSO₄), Sodium Fluoride (NaF), Potassium dichromate (K₂Cr₂O₇), Diphenylamine indicator, Kjeldhal tabs, Boric acid, Absolute ethanol, Bromolysol green methyl red, Sodium hydroxide, Nitric acid, acetic acid, magnesium sulphate, gum Arabic, barium chloride. Others are Potassium chloride (KCl), Sodium hydroxide (NaOH), Hydrochloric acid (HCl) and Phenolphthalein indicator.

Proximate analysis: This is performed by weighting, heating and burning a small sample of waste to determine the moisture content (M', in weight percent (w/o)), volatile matter and ash content; by driving off the free moisture at ~ 107° C for approximately 1 hour (Weisman and Eckart, 1985) shown by equation (2).

$$C'_{f(w/o)} = 100 - \frac{[M'_{(w/o)} + V'_{(w/o)} + A'_{s(w/o)}]}{\dots} \quad (2)$$

Ultimate analysis: It is a quantitative evaluation of the total carbon (C'), hydrogen (H'), nitrogen (N'), sulphur (S'), oxygen (O') percentages after removal of the moisture and ash (Tabatabai, 1974; Page et al. 1982). This analysis is performed using classic oxidation, decomposition, and/or reduction technique to determine, C (carbon), H (hydrogen), N (nitrogen) and S (sulphur). Oxygen O' (w/o) is calculated by difference using the equation as below (Weisman and Eckart 1985):

$$O'_{(w/o)} = 100 - \frac{[C'_{(w/o)} + H'_{(w/o)} + N'_{(w/o)} + S'_{(w/o)} + M'_{o(w/o)} + A'_{s(w/o)}]}{\dots} \quad (3)$$

Heating value or calorific value: The ash free, dry heating value can be calculated to within 2% accuracy by using the Dulong- Berthelot formula (Weisman and Eckart 1985):

$$Q_d = 81.37C' + 345 \left[H' - \frac{(O' + N' - 1)}{8} \right] + 22.2S \quad (4)$$

All data interpretation, calculations and graphs were carried out and generated using Microsoft Excel, 2007.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Quantification of the municipal solid waste generation in the study area is approximated to an average of 1.2 kg of refuse per person per day in the study area. Physical characteristics of the refuse as well as the proximate and ultimate analyses results in each of the cities with higher population density are shown in Figure (1) and Tables (1 and 2) respectively.

Table 1: Proximate analysis of waste samples in the study area.

Locality	Elements (%)			
	Moisture (w/o)*	Volatile matter (w/o)	Ash (w/o)	Fixed Carbon (w/o)
Damaturu	21.917	28.670	35.130	14.283
Maiduguri	21.830	25.120	30.830	22.220
Bauchi	24.326	22.450	31.770	21.454

* weight percent

Table 2: Ultimate analysis of waste samples in the study area.

Locality	Elements (%)				
	C (w/o)	H (w/o)	N (w/o)	S (w/o)	O (w/o)
Damaturu	21.946	0.210	1.205	0.052	19.540
Maiduguri	20.990	0.490	1.839	0.068	23.953
Bauchi	23.239	0.420	0.847	0.016	19.382

The calorific value (CV) of refuse (fuel) is the property of fundamental importance. It is a complex function of the elemental composition of the refuse or waste.

The variation in the CVs of refuse (Figure 2) was due to differences in the gradation of the constituent materials. The refuse LCV in Maiduguri with the highest population density is lower than the one in Damaturu which has a relatively lower population density. The differences in CVs are a bit significant even though these cities are in the same eco- zones while their population densities are not the same. In all the cases incineration process needed supplementary fuel because their CVs are lower than the 7.50 MJ/kg to 12.00 MJ/kg (an acceptable recommended range suggested by Whiting (2002)).

Figure 2: Calorific value (CV) of waste in the study area

Population density and geographic locations are not real determining factors as whether refuse quality may change or not but rather the life style of the population and their level of awareness towards waste management techniques. The generation would be influenced greatly by the mentioned factors; however, previous researches data are lacking for comparative purposes. A municipal solid waste incinerator of the parallel flow type, able to treat 8 tonnes of moist refuse and produce about 21.30 GJ of net, usable heat per hour, was found to be suitable to the study area (Figure 3).

This behaviour would help in adjusting and setting the waste treatment plant or incinerator in case of lower moisture contents by modifying the air supplies and altering the supplementary fuel quantity supply rates.

Figure 3: Suggested conceptual design of the municipal solid waste incinerator

CONCLUSION

The following conclusions were made based on the findings of this work:

1. Knowledge of household waste composition is an essential tool in order to properly plan its management.
2. Physical characterization showed that wood, grass, metal, plastic and paper were the constituents of all waste samples in the study area, but in varying proportions. Proximate and ultimate analyses of refuse in the area of study showed refuse characteristics as: Moisture: Volatile matter: Ash content: Fixed carbon: as 21.830: 25.120: 30.830: 22.220 and 21.917: 28.670: 35.130: 14.283 for Maiduguri and Damaturu respectively.
3. Average daily municipal solid waste generation was found to be about 1.2 kg per person per day.
4. Population density and geographic locations are not real determining factors as whether refuse quality may change or not but rather the life style of the population and the level of awareness of the population towards waste management.
5. The CVs were low and found to fall below the limit for the production of steam in electricity generation, therefore not to be able to sustain an industrial incineration process. To make up to the low

- CVs and avoid the problems of quenching and discontinuity in an incineration process, a supplementary fuel; bagasse, weeds; is needed.
6. The knowledge of the refuse CV alone is not enough to conclude whether the refuse will burn rapidly and effectively or not. Its moisture content is an essential determining parameter.

REFERENCES

- Adeyemi A. S., Olorunfemi J. F. and Adewoye T. O. (2004) *Waste scavenging in third World cities: A case study of Ilorin, Nigeria. The Environmentalist*, 21(2), 93-96. Springer Netherlands
- Agunwamba J. C., Ukpai O. K. and Onyebuanyi I. C. (1998) *Solid waste management in Onitsha. Waste Management and Research*, 16(1), 23-31
- Coker A. O.; Sridhar M. K. C. and Martins E. A. (2003) Management of septic sludge in southwest Nigeria, Proceedings of the 29th WEDC International Conference, Abuja, Nigeria; pp: 13-15.
- Daskalopoulos E., Badr O. and Probert S. (1998) An integrated approach to municipal solid waste management. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 24(1), pgs: 33-50
- Dauda Mohammed and Osita O. O. (2003) Solid Waste Management and Re-use in Maiduguri, Nigeria, Proceedings of the 29th WEDC International Conference, Abuja, Nigeria; pp: 20-23.
- Ehrlich Paul R, and Ehrlich Anne H. (1972) *Population, Resource, and Environment: Success in Human Ecology*. 2nd edition. H. Fressman and Co. San Francisco.
- Ikuponisi Francis S. (2006) *Status of Renewable Energy in Nigeria*. An international Conference on Making renewable Energy a Reality. ONE SKY- Canadian Institute of Sustainable Living, November 21-27 2006
- Jekayinfa, S. O. and Omisakin, O. S. (2005) The energy potentials off Some Agricultural Wastes as local Fuel materials in Nigeria. *Agricultural Engineering International: the CIGR Ejournal*. Vol.VII. Manuscript EE 05 003. May 2005
- Lee C. C. and Huffman G. L. (2001)*Solid Waste Calculations: Thermodynamics used in Environmental Engineering*. U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, Cincinnati, Ohio, pp: 2.47 part 2
- Mengiseny E. Kaseva and Josia L. Moirana (2010) Problems of solid waste management on Mount Kilimanjaro: A challenge to tourism. *Waste Management and Research*. Vol. 28; Issue 8; pp: 695-704
- Mudzafar Juwita (1996)*Waste Management in Developing Countries*. The Warmer Bulletin No 49, May. National Bureau for Statistics (2006) *The National Population Census*. Annual report, Nigeria, 01-07
- Ogaji S.O.T., S.D. Probert, A.H. Igoni and M.J. Ayotamuno (2007) Municipal solid-waste in Port Harcourt. *Applied Energy*, 84(6)
- Oumarou M. B., Dauda M. And Sulaiman A. T (2011) Experimental Characterization of Municipal Solid Wastes for Energy generation in North Eastern Nigeria; Proceedings of the 2nd National Water and Sanitation Conference, Kaduna Nigeria, pp.; 234-240
- Page A. L., R. H. Miller and D. R. Keeney (1982) *Methods of Soil Analysis-Part 2 Chemical and Microbiological Properties*. Second Edition
- Paolo S. Calabro (2010) The effect of separate collection of municipal solid waste on the lower colorific value of the residual waste. *Waste management and Research*. Vol 28, Issue 8, August; pp: 754-758
- Syngenta Foundation for Sustainable Agriculture (SFSA) (2007)*Sustainable innovation in agriculture: A Background to The Sahel and the semiarid region*. Helika Limited, UK.
- Tabatabai M. A. (1974) Determination of Sulphates in Water Samples. *Sulphur Institute Journal*. No.10 pp: 11-13

Weisman Joel and Roy Eckart (1985) *Modern Power Plant Engineering*. 2nd edition, Prentice Hall International, New Delhi

Whiting K. (2002) *Large scale MSW incineration Technologies, In: Annual short course on Incineration of municipal Waste Report*. pp: 1-37 University of Leeds, Department of Fuel and Energy, Leeds, UK.

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